

Research Article

Development of Wearable, Buoy Suit (BS) for Offshore Workplace Environment

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Abstract: Offshore workers such as repairing oil rigs and working on cruise ships are always exposed to the risk of hurting themselves accidentally. Many types of equipment are provided to these workers to lower the effect that happens, but that does not guarantee the health and safety of the worker when an emergency such as an explosion happens. The product we develop is a wearable that is created specifically for the safety reasons of workers. The advantages that our product can bring are increasing the trust of workers during working thus boosting the efficiency and quality of the work. The benefit of this product can be utilized by the community including the government and non-government groups. Generally, the development of this wearable is aligned with minimum safety standards and requirements for safety equipment on board ships provided by the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS).

Keywords: Emergency; Health; Offshore; Safety; Worker.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The term offshore can be referred to as any (business) activity that takes place outside an entity's home base, which means the location can be in any country, territory, or jurisdiction. There are many jobs in the offshore sector, including drilling engineers, offshore technicians and crane operators. The working shift in the offshore sector is not the same as the typical working hour pattern. For example, the working shift on an oil rig is 12 hours on and 12 hours off, because the oil rig operations are 24 hours a day and 7 days a week (Global Resources Network, 2024).

While working in the offshore sector seems like a dream job for most people because the pay is always higher compared to the job onshore, some risks concern the majority of people who are applying or involved in this sector. The most common risks associated with the offshore sector are fire, explosion and chemical exposure. (Oteplace, 2024)

The chemicals exposure such as chlorine, benzene, ammonia and hydrogen sulphide, often happen to the workers. The exposure usually takes place when handling and transporting hazardous materials, maintenance and cleaning operations, inadequate ventilation in confined spaces, and use of outdated equipment and vessels. Exposure to these chemicals for a certain period can lead to severe health issues such as internal bleeding, unconsciousness and death (Schechter, Shaffer & Harris, 2024).

Explosions are always linked with the oil and gas industry, especially oil rigs. The main factor that causes this to happen is blowouts, in which the control over pressure in the well is lost leading to unchecked release of oil or gas. Other factors that can also contribute to this issue are malfunction of the machines, weather and neglect. This accident always affects the health of workers and the environment surrounding it. Then it will cost a fortune to clean up the mess and recovery process (Arnold & Itkin LLP., 2015).

The ideal wearable use during working is extremely important to maintaining the overall quality of work, environment and health of the worker. The produced wearable, named Bouy Suit (BS), helps in improving the safety of the worker while also protecting the environment. This BS is equipped with various features while still following the requirements stated by the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) (IMO, 2019)

1.1 Objective

This wearable aims to lower the effect of the accidents or injuries that happen to offshore workers in the workplace environment. The development of this suit is aligned with the minimum requirement provided by the agency that is responsible for the regulation of appliances and apparatus used in this field.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Nomex IIIA is common and widely used and helps to shield the wearer from flames, flash fires and electric arcs. Nomex IIIA is durable, lightweight, and provides permanent flame resistance that won't wash out or wear away and can maintain the temperature during cold weather. The suit includes a built-in buoyancy device at both arms, designed to support body weight and provide stable buoyancy. TPU material is used because it has strong fabric, is durable and waterproof. It can last several hours to a day in moderate sea conditions. The buoy is equipped with a mechanical trigger, which is a pin. It is designed to be pulled by the user to activate the buoy. To deflate or re-pack the life jacket, pull the trigger or release mechanism and press or pull additional components to return it to a compact state.

A plastic whistle is ideal for harsh environments because it won't freeze in the cold, doesn't conduct heat or cold, floats in liquids, resists corrosion from salt and chlorine, and produces a loud, high-decibel sound. Retroreflective tape boosts safety by reflecting light to its source, making wearers highly visible to moving vehicles in low-light conditions. The BC95-G signal chip is compact (23.6mm × 19.9mm × 2.2mm) and rugged, ideal for space-sensitive applications. Its ultra-low power consumption

supports a wide range of uses, while its extended temperature range (-40°C to +85°C) ensures reliable performance. It offers comprehensive SMS and data transmission services.

3. FINDINGS

The primary goal of the research was to design a suit that enhances safety and performance for offshore workers who are at risk when they fall into the sea. We aimed to ensure the suit meets safety standards and addresses the needs of offshore workers effectively. Since there are so many variables to consider when working at an oil rig at sea, safety needs to be a top priority (Altomonte, 2024).

3.1 *Benefit to Mankind*

In the offshore sector, there are a lot of machines and chemicals involved, which may lead to accidents and can cause harm to workers. There are also times that accidents happen such as explosions and may cause these workers to jump into water. To prevent any potential injuries including chemical or machinery injuries, a protective a needed to cover the area that is exposed to these hazards. The solutions that we present are suitable for use by government and non-government agencies to ensure the safety of their worker thus protecting the quality of work produced, especially in an oil rig environment, where explosions usually take place.

3.2 *Potential of Commercialisation*

Potential clients can be expected from government bodies (search and rescue organizations, environmental protection agencies, research departments) and non-government bodies (shipping companies, oil and gas companies, renewable energy companies).

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the survey conducted, we found out that the majority of the respondents believe that buoy suits equipped with GPS and safety features would significantly improve worker safety in offshore environments with 88.40%. Next, 84.80% support companies investing more in protective gear like buoy suits, even if it raises initial costs. Meanwhile, 90.20% think the potential environmental benefits of reducing accidents justify the higher costs of buoy suits in offshore industries. 91.10% feel more confident working in high-risk environments if they are equipped with a buoy suit. Lastly, 84.80% think the commercialization of buoy suits should be expanded to other industries beyond offshore work.

5. CONCLUSION

Overall, this development is consistent with the requirements stated by the agency responsible for equipment and applications regulation, International Organization for Standardization ISO 16204: "Durability", ISO 15544: "Emergency response" and ISO 21457: "Materials selection".

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References

- Altomonte, L. (2024, May 17). *A guide to offshore safety*. SafetyCulture. <https://safetyculture.com/topics/offshore-safety/>
- Arnold & Itkin LLP. (2015). *Arnold & Itkin*. <https://www.offshoreinjuryfirm.com/oil-rig-explosions/common-causes-of-explosions/#:~:text=Negligence%20in%20maintaining%20equipment%2C%20such>
- Global Resources Network. (2024, February 10). *What to expect when you get offshore*. Global Resources Network | Offshore Drilling Recruitment. <https://www.grndrilling.com/post/what-to-expect-when-you-get-offshore#:~:text=Your%20experience%20of%20arriving%20offshore,however%20most%20people%20quickly%20adapt!>
- IMO. (2019). *International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS), 1974*. Imo.org. [https://www.imo.org/en/About/Conventions/Pages/International-Convention-for-the-Safety-of-Life-at-Sea-\(SOLAS\)](https://www.imo.org/en/About/Conventions/Pages/International-Convention-for-the-Safety-of-Life-at-Sea-(SOLAS))
- Oteplace. (2024). *Risks of working on an offshore oil rig: Fire, blowouts, and more*. Oteplace - Safety Equipment Marketplace. <https://www.oteplace.com/en/Blog-risks-working-offshore-rig#:~:text=One%20of%20the%20most%20common>
- Schechter, Shaffer & Harris. (2024, July 4). *The 5 most common toxic chemical exposures maritime workers face*. Maintenance and Cure. <https://maintenanceandcure.com/maritime-blog/the-5-most-common-maritime-toxic-chemical-exposures-maritime-workers-face/>
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